

Dynamic strain measurement of a lab-scale tidal turbine in elevated levels of homogeneous turbulent inflow

Mohd Hanzla, and Arindam Banerjee¹

¹Atlantic Marine Energy Center, Lehigh University, Bethlehem, PA, USA

Tidal flows in highly energetic sites are known to have flow asymmetries and elevated levels of free-stream turbulence. The dynamic nature of flow in these tidal sites significantly impacts turbine performance and wake development and presents a crucial source of induced fatigue loading on the blades. A detailed understanding of blade loading at elevated levels of inflow turbulence, specifically the influence of turbulence intensity (Ti) and integral length scale (L_u), is crucial for prolonging the design life cycles of the blades. To address this, we examine the real-time strain measurement along the span of a lab-scale horizontal axis tidal turbine (diameter, $D = 0.28\text{m}$) subjected to elevated turbulent inflow conditions. Optical Fiber Bragg Grating (FBG) sensors are attached to the leading and trailing edges of the in-house clamp-shell designed blades for strain measurements. A solid epoxy with a very high strain transfer efficiency attaches the *FBGs* to the blade surfaces, enabling continuous real-time strain measurement of the blades subjected to elevated turbulence. For mimicking the tidal site-conditions, the Tidal Turbulence Testing Facility (T^3F) housed at Lehigh University is used, which can recreate site-specific turbulent characteristics in its open surface, recirculating water tunnel using an active grid turbulence generator. The turbine with *FBGs* fastened on its blade is then subjected to three inflow conditions: quasi-laminar ($Ti \sim 2\%$), *elevated-Ti* ($Ti \sim 12-14\%$, $L_u \sim 0.35D$), and *elevated-Ti- L_D* having similar Ti as *elevated-Ti* case but higher integral length scale ($\sim D$). The latter allows us to differentiate the effect of a larger integral length scale from elevated turbulence. We will discuss detailed measurements and estimates of blade root bending moments for the inflow cases mentioned above. The experimental findings will provide valuable insights into optimizing turbine blade design for enhanced durability and performance in turbulent tidal environments.